

1 **Comparing phenotypic manifolds with Kompot: Detecting differential abundance and gene**
2 **expression at single-cell resolution**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17

18 Kompot is a statistical framework for holistic comparison of multi-condition single-cell datasets,
19 supporting both differential abundance and differential expression. Differential abundance captures
20 changes in how cells populate the phenotypic manifold across conditions, while differential expression
21 identifies condition-specific changes in gene regulation that may be localized to particular regions of that
22 manifold. Kompot models the distribution of cells and gene expression as continuous functions over a
23 low-dimensional representation of cell states, enabling single-cell resolution inference with calibrated
24 uncertainty estimates. Applying Kompot to aging murine bone marrow, we identified a continuum of shifts
25 in hematopoietic stem cell and mature cell states, transcriptional remodeling of monocytes independent
26 of compositional changes, and divergent regulation of oxidative stress response genes across cell types.
27 By capturing both global and cell-state-specific effects of perturbation, Kompot reveals how aging
28 reshapes cellular identity and regulatory programs across the hematopoietic landscape. This framework
29 is broadly applicable to dissecting condition-specific effects in complex single-cell landscapes.

30 **Introduction**

31 Multi-condition single-cell datasets offer new opportunities to dissect how mutations or other
32 perturbations affect both differentiation trajectories and disease phenotypes¹⁻⁴. Systematic analyses of
33 such datasets require characterization of two key aspects of condition-induced variability: differential
34 abundance and differential expression.

35 Differential abundance refers to differences in the composition of cell states between two conditions (**Fig.**
36 **1A, B**). Even in the absence of overt phenotypic shifts such as loss or gain of broad cell types, changes
37 in the frequency of specific cell states can provide early indicators of disease^{5, 6} and response to
38 treatment^{7, 8}. These changes are often nuanced and cell-type specific, necessitating statistical
39 approaches that rigorously assess significance while accounting for underlying biological variability.

40 Perturbations can also reshape the phenotypic landscape itself through differential expression, where
41 gene expression changes that would be unlikely or impossible in unperturbed conditions can emerge⁹
42 (**Fig. 1A, C**). These transcriptional responses reveal condition-specific molecular programs and
43 regulatory networks that often manifest as subtle yet systematic changes across multiple states⁹ and can
44 frequently be masked by the inherent variability within biological systems .

45 Several computational approaches have been developed for comparative analysis of multi-condition
46 single-cell data with differential abundance receiving greater attention¹⁰⁻¹⁵. A number of these methods
47 rely on discretizations such as clustering cells into discrete groups to stabilize variability estimates. While
48 facilitating interpretation, such discretizations lead to loss in resolution when changes are gradual or
49 occur along continuous trajectories (**Supp. Fig. 1A**). Additionally, many existing methods lack principled
50 significance measures, making it difficult to distinguish genuine biological signals from technical noise.

51 Here, we introduce Kompot, a novel computational framework that provides a continuous and statistically
52 rigorous approach for differential abundance and differential expression testing using multi-condition
53 single-cell data. Kompot leverages Gaussian Process (GP) modeling to estimate continuous functions
54 across the cell-state space. This approach enables quantification of differential abundance and
55 differential expression at single-cell resolution, while incorporating uncertainty estimates to provide
56 statistically calibrated comparisons. By addressing both aspects of multi-condition analysis within a
57 unified statistical framework, Kompot provides a comprehensive toolkit for extracting biological insights
58 from increasingly complex single-cell datasets across a range of biological systems.

59

60 **Results**

61 **Overview of the Kompot modeling framework**

62 A single-cell RNA-seq dataset provides a snapshot of cellular states in a biological system, with the
63 molecules measured representing a sample of the transcriptome of the cell. To characterize the system
64 and compare it to similar systems under different conditions (such as mutations or other perturbations),
65 we need to understand what this data tells us about the true composition of transcribed genes in a cell
66 and the true distribution of cell states in the system. With Kompot we leverage high-dimensional,
67 continuous cell-state representations and Bayesian Inference to learn both, the composition of the system
68 and transcriptomes of each cell, enabling a holistic comparison of biological systems at single-cell
69 resolution with uncertainty quantification. This comparison is divided into differential cell-state abundance
70 that reflect changes in cell-state composition, and differential-expression that reflect changes in the
71 transcriptome of cells in equivalent states.

72 The input to Kompot is a latent representation of co-embedded multi-condition single-cell data. This latent
73 representation can incorporate batch effect correction^{16, 17} to ensure that cell states considered equivalent
74 share similar locations in that state space (**Supp. Fig. 1B**). From this foundation, Kompot employs

75 diffusion maps¹⁸ to derive a cell-state representation with biologically meaningful structure (**Fig. 1A**).
76 Diffusion maps are particularly effective for single-cell analysis as they capture the intrinsic geometry of
77 the data while providing biologically meaningful measures of cell-to-cell distance^{19,20}. This distance metric
78 supports both accurate local abundance estimation and principled information sharing when mapping
79 from cell-state space to gene expression, enabling the statistical comparisons at the core of Kompot's
80 differential testing framework.

81

82 **Kompot differential abundance testing**

83 To quantify differences in cell-state composition between conditions, Kompot first constructs condition-
84 specific density functions on the diffusion map representation. For each condition, Kompot computes a
85 separate continuous density function (**Fig. 1B, Supp. Fig. 2A-B**) using our Mellon framework²¹. Mellon
86 leverages nearest-neighbor distances within a Gaussian Process model to estimate continuous density
87 functions that capture the distribution of cells across the state space²¹. The continuous nature of these
88 density estimates enables evaluation at any position within the cell-state space, including states
89 predominantly observed in the alternate condition (**Supp. Fig. 2B**). By computing the ratio of density
90 estimates at corresponding positions in the cell-state space, Kompot derives a measure of differential
91 abundance that quantifies the fold-change in cell density between conditions at single-cell resolution
92 (**Supp. Fig. 2C**).

93 While the ratio of density estimates provides a measure of fold-change, rigorous comparison between
94 conditions requires statistical assessment of significance. Kompot addresses this challenge by computing
95 uncertainty estimates for each density function. These uncertainty estimates account for two critical
96 factors: limited data availability in regions of the cell-state space and inherent uncertainty through the
97 sparse function representation. By incorporating these uncertainty estimates into the statistical
98 framework, Kompot calculates posterior tail probabilities (PTPs), an alternative for p-values, for
99 differential abundance at each cell state. This enables the generation of volcano plots for differential
100 abundance testing where each point represents a single cell-state (**Fig. 1B**), allowing for threshold-based
101 significance assessments. Thus, Kompot can identify subtle cell-state transitions and rare subpopulations
102 that would likely be undetected by clustering-based approaches, providing insights into the continuous
103 spectrum of cellular responses to perturbations (**Fig. 1D**).

104

105 **Kompot differential expression testing**

106 For differential expression testing between conditions, Kompot constructs condition-specific mappings
107 from cell-states to gene expression space (**Fig. 1A, C**). These mappings are computed using Gaussian
108 Processes (GPs)²², by predicting log-transformed gene expression as a continuous function of the
109 diffusion map coordinates. The non-linear relationship between diffusion maps and gene expression is
110 effectively captured by GPs²², essentially serving as a rigorous approach to gene expression imputation.
111 The continuous nature of these mapping functions allows Kompot to estimate gene expression in one
112 condition for cell states observed in another, producing counterfactual expression profiles that reflect how
113 those same cell states would behave under different conditions (**Fig. 1C**). By computing the ratio between
114 the actual expression in a cell and its counterfactual expression, Kompot quantifies gene expression-fold
115 changes for every gene at single-cell resolution across the entire phenotypic landscape (**Fig. 1C**).

116 Given the large number of genes evaluated, we require a robust significance measure that allows us to
117 identify the most relevant genes, accounting for both uncertainty in the gene expression function and
118 statistical interdependence of imputed values. Kompot therefore employs the Mahalanobis distance,
119 which measures the distance of a point from a multivariate normal distribution, considering both variance
120 and covariance²³. It effectively measures how many standard deviations a gene expression shift is away

121 from expected variation, while accounting for the correlation structure between neighboring cell states,
122 making it an ideal significance measure for differential expression. Kompot therefore uses Mahalanobis
123 distances as the score in a quasi-volcano plot (**Fig. 1C**) to identify significantly differentially expressed
124 genes either in the full population of cells or in specific subsets (**Fig. 1D**).

125

126 Differential Abundance in Aging Bone Marrow

127 Aging is a compelling biological context for evaluating differential abundance methods, as it induces
128 progressive and often subtle shifts in cellular composition rather than dramatic phenotypic
129 transformations. Hematopoiesis has emerged as a particularly informative system for studying aging²⁴,
130 characterized by declining stem cell function²⁵, reduced lymphocyte production²⁶, and increased
131 susceptibility to myeloid malignancies²⁷. To investigate these age-related changes, we generated a novel
132 scRNA-seq dataset of murine bone marrow at 10, 63, and 103 weeks of age, representing young, middle-
133 aged, and older timepoints (**Supp. Fig. 3A**). After quality control verification (**Supp. Fig. 3B, C**), we
134 successfully identified most hematopoietic cell types across all ages (**Fig. 2A, B, Supp. Fig. 4**), providing
135 us with a rich dataset to characterize cell-state changes and gene expression changes in aging
136 hematopoiesis using Kompot.

137 We applied Kompot differential abundance testing on our aging hematopoiesis dataset to determine age-
138 dependent composition changes (**Fig. 2C-E**). We first derived a unified cell-state representation for all
139 cells using diffusion maps. We then calculated age-specific density functions using the subsets of cells
140 from each timepoint (**Supp. Fig. 5A-B**). We evaluated these individual density functions at all cell-states
141 in the dataset to derive condition-specific densities and associated uncertainties (**Supp. Fig. 5C-D**). This
142 approach enabled pairwise comparisons that quantify age-related changes in cell-type composition (**Fig.**
143 **2C-D**). A key advantage of our framework is the ability to set thresholds based on both effect size and
144 statistical significance at single-cell resolution, allowing for identification of cell states with significant
145 differential abundance rather than relying solely on fold-change cutoffs (**Fig. 2C-E**).

146 Our analysis revealed significant expansions and contractions in distinct cell populations over time.
147 Comparing young to old mice, we observed an expansion of the hematopoietic stem cell (HSC)
148 compartment and a marked shift from naïve to memory cells in both B-cell and T-cell compartments (**Fig.**
149 **2F-G**). The depletion of naïve B-cells and an enrichment of memory B-cells in older mice is a well-
150 characterized phenomenon of hematopoietic aging²⁶. This shift reflects fundamental changes in
151 differentiation dynamics: naïve B-cells rely on a continuous influx from hematopoietic progenitors,
152 whereas memory B-cells accumulate over time due to antigen exposure. The observed decline in naïve
153 B-cells reflects the reduced lymphoid differentiation potential of aged HSCs²⁸, while the expansion of
154 memory B-cells, including age-associated B-cells, is driven by persistent immune activation²⁹. Similarly,
155 the T-cell compartment displayed a significant reduction in naïve T-cells with a concurrent increase in
156 memory T-cells, a hallmark of immunosenescence that contributes to diminished adaptive immune
157 responses in aging³⁰.

158 An increased accumulation of hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) is the most significant change we
159 observed in the progenitor cells (**Fig. 2F-G**). Progressive enrichment of HSCs with age is a well-
160 documented phenomenon³¹. HSCs reside at the top of the hematopoietic hierarchy, maintaining blood
161 production through self-renewal and differentiation into mature immune and blood cells. With aging, HSC
162 function declines, leading to accumulation in the bone marrow while their ability to differentiate into
163 different lineages becomes impaired³¹. While the accumulation of aged HSCs has been previously
164 observed, it has traditionally been quantified using bulk measurements or clustering-based approaches.
165 We took advantage of the single-cell resolution of Kompot to better characterize the age-induced change
166 in HSCs. By comparing the differential abundance fold-change along pseudotime ordering¹⁹, we
167 observed that the expansion of HSC population is in fact a subtle shift in cell-state, rather than a global

168 increase in a predefined population (**Fig. 2H**). Specifically, HSCs in older mice progressively shift towards
169 a less differentiation-primed state, creating a continuum of altered stem cell states rather than a uniform
170 expansion (**Fig. 2H**). This subtle but consequential repositioning along the differentiation trajectory
171 provides a possible explanation for the functional decline in aged HSCs, revealing how changes in cell
172 abundance are accompanied by fundamental alterations in cellular function and developmental potential.

173 Comparing differential abundance results across ages, we observed that changes in mature cell
174 populations predominantly occurred between young and middle-aged mice (**Fig. 2D, Supp. Fig. 6A**),
175 while alterations in the HSC compartment were more pronounced between middle-aged and older mice
176 (**Fig. 2E, Supp. Fig. 6B**). This temporal separation suggests a sequential progression of aging, where
177 compositional shifts in differentiated cells precede fundamental changes in stem cell states. The early
178 alterations in mature immune cells may represent initial adaptive responses to aging, while the later HSC
179 changes potentially indicate more persistent reprogramming of the hematopoietic system.

180 Our results demonstrate the ability of Kompot to identify subtle but biologically meaningful abundance
181 changes between conditions. By combining a continuous representation of cell states with robust
182 statistical measures, Kompot enables precise detection of population-level changes while maintaining
183 single-cell resolution.

184

185 Differential Gene Expression in Aging Hematopoiesis

186 We applied Kompot differential expression testing on our mouse aging hematopoiesis dataset to
187 characterize age-related transcriptional changes (**Fig. 3**). We first inferred age-specific mapping functions
188 from diffusion map coordinates to log-normalized gene expression values, using the subset of cells from
189 each timepoint. We then used these mappings to impute gene expression and associated uncertainty at
190 all cell-states across the dataset. This enabled us to compute gene-level fold changes by comparing
191 observed expression values to their counterfactual predictions under alternative age conditions. To
192 assess significance, we calculated Mahalanobis distances for each gene across specified groups of cells,
193 quantifying deviations from expected variation while accounting for the covariate structure among
194 neighboring cell states. We excluded T and NK cells for this analysis since do not differentiate in the bone
195 marrow (**Fig. 3H**).

196 We first applied our approach to characterize gene expression changes in HSCs, a population known to
197 undergo functional and transcriptional changes with age³¹, by comparing HSCs from middle-aged to old-
198 aged mice (**Fig. 3A-B**). Aging in HSCs has been extensively studied, and the Hematopoietic Aging Atlas
199 has synthesized results from multiple datasets to identify genes consistently up- or downregulated with
200 age³². For each gene, this atlas assigns a consistency score that reflects the reproducibility of age-
201 associated expression changes across studies³². Kompot's differential expression results strongly
202 prioritized genes with the highest consistency scores in the Hematopoietic Aging Atlas, with genes
203 showing large fold changes and Mahalanobis distances highly enriched for reproducible aging signatures
204 (**Fig. 3C, Supp. Fig. 7**).

205 Our differential abundance analysis revealed that HSCs in older mice shift towards a less differentiated
206 state along the cell-state continuum (**Fig. 2H**). We next asked whether the genes differentially expressed
207 in aged HSCs reflected this shift. Indeed, we found that gene expression fold changes were structured
208 along the same continuum: genes exhibited larger fold changes in cell states that were more differentially
209 abundant (**Fig. 3D**). These results highlight the transcriptional changes in HSCs that accompany and
210 may underlie the shift toward a less differentiated state with age,

211 We next investigated age-related gene expression changes in mature cell types. We focused on changes
212 from young to old mice since the abundance changes in mature cell types were most pronounced in this
213 comparison (**Fig. 2D-F**). To distinguish expression changes from abundance-driven effects, we restricted

214 our analysis to cell types that *did not show significant compositional changes*. Monocytes exhibited clear
215 transcriptional changes despite stable abundance (**Fig. 3E-F**). Gene ontology analysis revealed that
216 downregulated genes were enriched in core monocyte/macrophage functions such as defense response
217 (**Fig. 3G**), consistent with their reduced functional capacity with age³³. In contrast, upregulated genes
218 were enriched for antigen processing and presentation pathways, driven by increased expression of MHC
219 class II genes (**Fig. 3G**), which have been implicated in age-related immune remodeling³⁴. Notably, our
220 results recapitulate findings from a previous study that identified H2-Aa, H2-Ab1, H2-Eb1, Cd74, and
221 Aw112010 as the top dysregulated genes in aging monocytes across both mice and humans, with only
222 *Igkc* surpassing H2-Eb1 in our ranking³⁴. The near-perfect agreement with experimentally validated gene
223 sets underscores the power of our differential expression testing approach to detect biologically
224 meaningful transcriptional shifts. Gene expression differences in other mature cell types were not as
225 pronounced but did show a tendency for upregulation of MHC Class II genes similar to monocytes (**Supp.**
226 **Fig. 8**).

227 Our use of Mahalanobis distance as a significance measure enables Kompot to identify genes that exhibit
228 coordinated but opposing changes across subpopulations. For example, consider a gene that is
229 upregulated in one cell type and downregulated in another. While the net fold change may be close to
230 zero, the Mahalanobis distance remains high, reflecting a statistically significant deviation from expected
231 variation if unaffected. This occurs because such a pattern is unlikely under the local covariance structure
232 of the cell-state space, where neighboring states are typically expected to exhibit similar expression
233 patterns. As a result, Kompot can detect structured differential expression that would be missed by
234 conventional fold-change-based approaches.

235 To test this capability, we applied Kompot differential expression testing between young and old cells
236 across all cell-types that differentiate in the bone marrow (**Fig. 3H-I**). The top genes with both high positive
237 fold change and high Mahalanobis distance were strongly enriched for MHC class II genes, consistent
238 with our monocyte-specific results and indicating that MHC class II upregulation is a general feature of
239 hematopoietic aging (**Fig. 3J**). Likewise, genes with high Mahalanobis distance and strong negative fold
240 change were consistently downregulated across multiple cell types (**Fig. 3J**). In contrast, genes ranked
241 highly by Mahalanobis distance but with low absolute fold change exhibited divergent expression patterns
242 across cell types, with upregulation in some and downregulation in others (**Fig. 3J**). To illustrate these
243 distinctions, we visualized expression levels of representative genes from each category across the cell-
244 state manifold (**Fig. 3K**). Genes selected by fold change showed broad, monotonic shifts in expression,
245 whereas Mahalanobis-selected genes revealed distinct, cell-type-specific regulation (**Fig. 3K**).

246 We next performed gene ontology analysis to assess the biological relevance of genes with high
247 Mahalanobis distance but low absolute fold change. Antioxidant activity emerged as the most significantly
248 enriched term (**Fig. 3L**), a pathway known to be impacted by aging³⁵. Notably, our results indicate that
249 while antioxidant activity is broadly impacted across hematopoietic cell types, the direction of expression
250 changes of the pathway genes varies across genes and cell types, suggesting a context-specific
251 adaptation to aging (**Fig. 3M**). Oxidative stress is a known driver of HSC dysfunction, promoting DNA
252 damage, apoptosis, and biased differentiation toward myeloid lineages³⁵. The differential expression of
253 antioxidant pathway genes observed in our study likely represents a compensatory mechanism to
254 mitigate reactive oxygen species (ROS) accumulation in aged HSCs³⁵.

255 These results demonstrate that Mahalanobis distance captures biologically meaningful heterogeneity in
256 gene expression and provides a powerful approach for aggregating structured expression differences
257 across cell states without requiring prior clustering, making it especially suited for complex, continuous
258 single-cell landscapes.

259

260 **Discussion**

261 Kompot provides a flexible statistical framework for quantifying condition-specific effects in single-cell
262 data, modeling both cell abundance and gene expression as continuous functions over the cell-state
263 manifold. By estimating condition-specific densities and expression profiles using Gaussian processes,
264 Kompot performs differential analysis at single-cell resolution while accounting for uncertainty and spatial
265 structure in the data. This approach supports biologically grounded interpretations of perturbation effects,
266 whether they manifest as global shifts in population structure, localized transcriptional responses, or
267 context-specific coordination between abundance and expression changes.

268 Applying Kompot to aging murine bone marrow revealed both well-established and previously
269 unrecognized features of hematopoietic aging. Kompot recapitulated known expansions in memory
270 lymphocytes and age-associated B cells, while resolving more subtle shifts in hematopoietic stem cell
271 states that do not correspond to discrete population changes. In the transcriptomic landscape, Kompot
272 uncovered gene expression programs that are either conserved or cell-type specific, including divergent
273 regulation of oxidative stress pathways. These findings demonstrate how modeling continuous
274 phenotypic structure supports more nuanced detection of biological change. Beyond aging, Kompot is
275 broadly applicable to studies of development, disease progression, and response to perturbation, where
276 condition-induced effects often unfold along continuous, high-dimensional trajectories.

277

278 **Methods**

279

280 **Kompot framework**

281 Kompot is a tool for comparing single-cell phenotypic manifolds across conditions. It provides frameworks
282 for both differential abundance testing and differential gene expression testing at single-cell resolution
283 using multi-condition datasets. Differential abundance testing enables the detection of abundance shifts
284 of cell-states across the phenotypic manifold, without requiring predefined cell-type boundaries. This is
285 achieved by estimating condition-specific cell-state densities using the Bayesian inference scheme
286 implemented in Mellon. In parallel, through differential gene expression testing, Kompot identifies gene
287 expression changes across the same manifold, capturing subtle but structured transcriptional shifts that
288 may vary across cell states and may not follow consistent directionality To do so, Kompot leverages the
289 Gaussian process inference implemented in Mellon to estimate condition-specific gene expression
290 functions for thousands of genes within minutes, while explicitly sharing information across neighboring
291 cell states to address sparsity and enable statistically meaningful comparisons

292

293 **Differential Abundance**

294 This section explains the methods of Kompot's differential abundance (DA) analysis framework. Our
295 density quantification relies on the Gaussian Process (**GP**) estimation implemented in Mellon. This
296 estimation process is a Bayesian inference that provides us with both a "best estimate" function that maps
297 each point in the cell-state space to a density value $\mu(x_i)$, and a quantification of uncertainty $\sigma(x_i)$. Since
298 we infer these quantities independently for each condition, the posterior distribution for the density
299 change from condition a to condition b at any cell state x_i is given by

$$300 \delta(x_i) \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\mu_b(x_i) - \mu_a(x_i), \sigma_a^2(x_i) + \sigma_b^2(x_i)\right).$$

301 Therefore, our density log-fold change is defined by $\mu_b(x_i) - \mu_a(x_i)$, and our uncertainty quantification
302 by $\sigma_a^2(x_i) + \sigma_b^2(x_i)$. Notably, using the correct intrinsic dimensionality, Mellon reports density in the unit
303 log number of cells per volume.

304 To make density values comparable across samples with different cell counts, we can transform this unit
305 into log fraction of cells per volume by subtracting the log total number of cells. Therefore, we normalize
306 density in Kompot using

$$307 \mu'_a(x_i) = \mu_a(x_i) - \log N_a$$

308 where N_a represents the total number of cells measured for condition a . For this normalization to be valid,
309 it is essential, that we assume the correct intrinsic dimensionality of the phenotypic manifold. To that end
310 we use Mellon dimensionality estimation that is assumed to be constant across the dataset.

311 Finally, we can define the Kompot's local density log-fold change statistic as

$$312 \Delta(x_i) = \mu_b(x_i) - \mu_a(x_i) - \log N_a / N_b.$$

313 Additionally, we provide a p-value-like significance value through the posterior tail probability (**PTP**). For
314 example, if the density change $\Delta(x_i)$ is positive, then we compute $\mathbb{P}(\delta(x_i) < 0)$, and $\mathbb{P}(\delta(x_i) > 0)$ when
315 $\Delta(x_i)$ is negative. The PTP quantifies the probability that the true fold change goes into the opposite
316 direction of our best estimate, given our data and modeling assumptions. Since our posterior distribution
317 is a normal distribution, the local Kompot PTP is given by:

318

$$PTP(x_i) = \Phi \left(\frac{-|\Delta(x_i)|}{\sqrt{\sigma_a^2(x_i) + \sigma_b^2(x_i)}} \right)$$

319 were Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

320

321 **Differential Expression**

322 Similar to the density differences, we also leverage Mellon's GP implementation (**Supp. Note 1**) for
 323 differential expression (DE) analysis. In contrast to the density inference algorithm, this DE method
 324 directly conditions the gene-expression functions on the measured data, as classically done in GPs. For
 325 each condition, the goal is to compute a gene-expression function that predicts an expression value for
 326 each gene at any location in the cell-state space, specific to that condition. These functions provide a
 327 smooth and continuous representation of gene expression across the manifold and allow for quantifying
 328 differential expression between conditions at any point in state space, effectively integrating all data
 329 points without requiring predefined cluster boundaries.

330 The resulting gene-expression functions and uncertainty estimation can be used equivalently to the cell-
 331 state density functions to compute local gene-expression differences, featuring local fold change and
 332 PTP. However, apart from the question in which cell-state a gene may be differentially expressed, we
 333 want to answer if a gene asserts any significant DE within a cell population or across the entire cell-state
 334 space, effectively aggregating measurements across multiple cells.

335 This comes with an important caveat: The GP based gene-expression functions are an imputation that
 336 already accumulates measurements of multiple cells, and the resulting gene-expression values $f(x_i)$ at
 337 different cell states x_i are not independent measurements that can be aggregated directly. This caveat
 338 can be addressed very directly through Mellon's uncertainty quantification: It covers not only the variance
 339 for a function value $f(x_i)$ but also the covariance to other function values $f(x_j)$ based on the similarity of
 340 x_i and x_j . This covariance can be understood as a statistical connection between the expressions of two
 341 cell states that comes from our assumption that genes change expression smoothly throughout cell-state
 342 space. Formally, under our modelling assumption, the true gene expression values $f(x)$ at cell states
 343 $x = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^m$ are distributed according to a posterior

344
$$f(x) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(x), \Sigma(x)).$$

345 Therefore, the significance for an expressional change between two conditions k and l can be quantified
 346 through the Mahalanobis distance (**Supp. Note 2**):

347
$$D(a, b) = \sqrt{(\mu_a - \mu_b)^T (\Sigma_a + \Sigma_b)^{-1} (\mu_a - \mu_b)}$$

348 Notably, this adequately accounts for redundancy, as adding a nearly identical cell state contribute nearly
 349 nothing to the value of this statistic, while more distinct cell-states have a larger contribution. We leverage
 350 this to our advantage. By producing a fixed set of landmarks, using k-means clustering, we limit the
 351 evaluation of the gene-expression function and the size of the covariance matrix to a fixed size. By using
 352 a fixed number of steps and k++ initialization, both the clustering and the GP only grow linearly in run-
 353 time with the number of cells. Notably, k-means grows with $O(t \times k \times d \times n)$ where t is the number of
 354 iterations, k the number of landmarks, d the dimensionality of the space, and n the number of cells.

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356

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358 Data analysis

359 Detailed descriptions of data generation and analysis described in the manuscript will be included in a
360 subsequent version of the manuscript.

361

362

363 **Data Availability**

364 Raw single-cell data for the murine aging hematopoiesis will be deposited to GEO. Processed anndata
365 object with annotations is available to download from Zenodo³⁶.

366

367 **Code Availability**

368 Kompot is available as a Python module at <https://github.com/settylab/Kompot>. Jupyter notebooks
369 detailing the usage of Kompot differential expression and differential abundance testing are available at
370 <https://github.com/settylab/kompot/tree/main/examples> and documentation at
371 <https://kompot.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

372

373 **Acknowledgements**

374 This study was supported by National Institute of General Medical Studies grant no. R35 GM147125 to
375 M.S.; National Cancer Institute grant no. R01CA292932, Mark Foundation for Cancer Research
376 Endeavor Award and Edward P. Evans Foundation Discovery Research Grant to S.C.L.; Brotman Baty
377 Institute Pilot Award and Translational Data Science IRC New Collaboration Award to M.S. and S.C.L;
378 National Institute of General Medicine Studies grant no. T32GM136534 to E.T.; National Institutes of
379 Health grant no. ORIP S10OD028685 to support high-performance computing at the Fred Hutchinson
380 Cancer Center.

381

382 **Competing Interests**

383 The authors declare no competing interests.

384

Figures

386

387

388 Figure 1: Overview of Kompot's framework for differential abundance and expression
389 analysis.

390 (A) Illustration of high-dimensional single-cell transcriptomic data from two conditions, projected into a
391 shared low-dimensional cell-state space using diffusion maps.

392 (B) Differential abundance analysis in Kompot. Condition-specific cell-state densities with associated
393 uncertainty estimates are computed and compared to yield density log-fold changes. Significance is
394 quantified using posterior tail probability (PTP), visualized in a quasi-volcano plot.

395 (C) Differential expression analysis. Left: schematic of inferred phenotypic manifolds for both conditions
396 with counterfactual cell pairs illustrating expression comparison. Middle: gene-specific differences are
397 illustrated for one example gene, showing condition-specific expression levels, statistical
398 interdependence, and uncertainty. Right: A quasi-volcano plot summarizes gene-level results with the
399 average log-fold change on the x-axis and Mahalanobis distance (accounting for variance and
400 covariance) as a multivariate significance score on the y-axis.

401 (D) Visualization of differential abundance (left) and differential expression (right) across the cell-state
402 space, colored by log-fold change magnitude.

403

404

405 **Figure 2: Kompot differential abundance analysis in aging hematopoiesis.**

406 (A) UMAP projection of aging murine bone marrow scRNA-seq dataset, colored by medium-resolution
 407 cell types.

408 (B) UMAPs highlighting cells from mice grouped by age: Young (10 weeks), Mid (63 weeks), and Old
 409 (103 weeks).

410 (C) Differential abundance results for the Young to Mid (left), Young to Old (middle) and Mid to Old (right)
 411 comparisons. Quasi-cell volcano plot with density log-fold change on the x-axis and Posterior Tail
 412 Probabilities (PTP) on the y-axis. Significantly different cell-states (absolute log fold change > 1, PTP <
 413 10^{-3}) are highlighted by their cell type annotations from (A).

414 (D) UMAPs displaying the estimated local density log-fold changes across the full joint cell-state space
 415 derived from all samples (Young, Mid, and Old) for comparisons in C.

416 (E) UMAPs highlighting the subset of cell states with statistically significant abundance changes, as
 417 defined by the thresholds shown in the volcano plots in C.

418 (F) Differential abundance volcano plots showing density log-fold changes across cells, stratified by major
 419 cell type and colored by subtype in the Young to Old comparison. y-axis indicates posterior tail probability.
 420 Violin plots in the background indicate abundance of cells at the respective density log-fold change in
 421 this group.

422 (G) Direction and magnitude of abundance changes per cell type in the Young to Old comparison. Bars
423 show the fraction of significantly changing cell-states within each annotated cell type, color-coded by the
424 direction of change. Cell types are ordered along a progenitor-to-mature axis.

425 (H) Kompot results for early hematopoietic progenitors. Left: UMAP highlighting HSC, and LMPP subsets.
426 Right: Scatterplot of cells colored by density log-fold change along pseudotime (x-axis), showing dynamic
427 abundance shifts during early differentiation.

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430 **Figure 3: Kompot differential expression analysis in aging hematopoiesis.**

431 (A) UMAP from Fig. 2A, with HSCs highlighted.

432 (B) Differential expression results for Mid to Old HSCs. Quasi-cell volcano plot with expression log-fold
 433 change on the x-axis and Mahalanobis distance on the y-axis. Significantly different genes (absolute log
 434 fold change > 0.15, Mahalanobis distance > 3) are highlighted.

435 (C) like (B) colored by weighted average of reported “Aging Consistency” using standard Gaussian Kernel
 436 after scaling x- and y-axis to standard deviation 1.

437 (D) Same plot as Fig. 2H, colored by Mid to Old HSC gene expression log fold change for a gene
 438 downregulated with age (Cd52, left) and an upregulated gene (Ifitm1, right).

439 (E) UMAP from Fig. 2A, with monocytes highlighted.

440 (F) Same as (B), for Young to Old monocytes.

441 (G) Gene ontology analysis from STRING³⁷ for downregulated genes (left) and upregulated genes (right)
 442 from Fig. 2F.

443 (H) UMAP for Fig. 2A, highlighting all cell types except T and NK cells

444 (I) Differential expression results for all cells in Fig. 2H for Young to Old comparisons. Top 10 genes with
445 positive fold change and high Mahalanobis distance are shown in red, bottom 10 genes with negative
446 fold change and high Mahalanobis distance are shown in blue, and genes with log absolute fold change
447 but high Mahalanobis distance are shown in green (absolute log fold change < 0.07 , Mahalanobis
448 distance > 6). 20 genes are labeled.

449 (J) Heatmap showing Young to Old gene expression log fold changes across different cell types for genes
450 highlighted in (I).

451 (K) Top: Imputed expression of gene H2-Q7 using young cells (left), using old cells (right) and fold change
452 from young to old (middle). Middle, Bottom: Same as the top row for Mef2c and Dynll1. These genes
453 serve as examples of genes with high positive fold change, high Mahalanobis but low absolute fold
454 change, and high negative fold change respectively.

455 (L) Gene ontology analysis using genes with high Mahalanobis distance and low absolute fold change
456 from (I).

457 (M) Heatmap showing Young to Old gene expression log fold changes across different cell types for
458 genes involved in antioxidant activity.

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